

Notes

Low Frequency Infrared Spectra of some Carbonyl Complexes of Rhodium(I)

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Infrared carbonyl stretching frequencies have been extensively used as the diagnostic tool for elucidating the structure of carbonyl complexes of transition metals. Other vibrational modes such as carbon-metal-carbon deformation (for dicarbonyls), metal-carbonyl deformation, δ_{M-C-O} and metal-carbon stretching frequencies, ν_{M-C} occurring below 700 cm^{-1} can also provide additional informations about the structural features of these compounds. However, this ir region¹⁻⁶ for these compounds has not been much studied. Browing *et al.*⁷ reported data on skeletal vibrations of different carbonyl complexes including for the compounds $[MX_2(CO)_2]^-$, where $M = \text{Rh}^I, \text{Ir}^I$; $X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-$. We report herein the ir data in the region 700–300 cm^{-1} for some carbonyl complexes of rhodium(I) of the types $[\text{Rh}(\text{N}-\text{N})(\text{CO})_2]\text{BF}_4$, $[\text{Rh}(\text{N}-\text{N})(\text{CO})_2][\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]$ and *trans*- $[\text{RhX}(\text{CO})(\text{R}_2\text{S}/\text{R}_2\text{SO})_2]$, where $\text{N}-\text{N} = 2,9$ -dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline (Me_2phen), 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline ($\text{NO}_2\text{-phen}$), 2,2'-biquinoline (biq); $\text{R}_2\text{S} = \text{dimethyl, di-}i\text{-propyl sulphide}$; $\text{R}_2\text{SO} = \text{dimethyl, di-}i\text{-propyl and di-}i\text{-butyl sulphoxide}$; $X = \text{Cl}^-$ and Br^- .

Results and Discussion

The ir data of the complexes of rhodium(I) in the region 700–300 cm^{-1} are given in the Table 1. We have selected the deformation modes for our discussion because they are easily identifiable and occur in the region comparatively free from other ligand vibrations. It may be noted that in *cis*- $[\text{RhX}_2(\text{CO})_2]^-$ ($X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-$) having C_{2v} symmetry, two types of vibrations⁷, namely $\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O}$ in-plane, $\delta_{(\text{M}-\text{C}-\text{O})_h}$ and out-of-plane, $\delta_{(\text{M}-\text{C}-\text{O})_v}$ bending and ν_{M-C} stretching vibrations (symmetric and antisymmetric) are ir active. Thus, four bands are expected for such complexes in the region 650–400 cm^{-1} and their occurrence should follow the order¹:

$$\delta_{(\text{M}-\text{C}-\text{O})_v} > \nu_{(\text{M}-\text{C})_{\text{sym}}} > \delta_{(\text{M}-\text{C}-\text{O})_h} > \nu_{(\text{M}-\text{C})_{\text{asym}}}$$

The bands are easily identifiable. Generally, the higher energy bands are of high intensity. Moreover, though some coupling between $\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O}$ deformation and $\text{Rh}-\text{C}$ stretching modes are expected⁸, it is not difficult to assign the bands to a given set of vibrations. Thus, in the spectra of di-

TABLE 1—LOW-FREQUENCY IR BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF Rh^I -CARBONYL COMPLEXES

Compd.	$\delta(\text{RhCO})_v$	$\nu(\text{RhC})_{\text{sym}}$	$\delta(\text{RhCO})_h$	$\nu(\text{RhC})_{\text{asym}}$	$\nu(\text{RhX})$ and other bands
$[\text{Rh}(\text{Me}_2\text{phen})(\text{CO})_2]\text{BF}_4$	610s	502m	485vw	460vw	522 ^a
$[\text{Rh}(\text{NO}_2\text{phen})(\text{CO})_2]\text{BF}_4$	600s	555vw	500vw	460vw	520 ^a
$[\text{Rh}(\text{Me}_2\text{phen})(\text{CO})_2][\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]$	610s	505s	490s	456vw	—
$[\text{Rh}(\text{NO}_2\text{phen})(\text{CO})_2][\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]$	605s 602s	525s	480s	465m	—
$[\text{Rh}(\text{biq})(\text{CO})_2][\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]$	610s 575w	500w	480s	—	—
$[\text{N}(i\text{-pr})_4][\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]^b$	622vs 598wsh	492vs	517m 496w	464w	—
$[\text{N}(i\text{-pr})_4][\text{RhBr}_2(\text{CO})_2]^b$	609vs 584sh	487vs	514m 496vs	449m	—
$[\text{Rh}(\text{SOX})(\text{CO})_2]^c$	590s	510w	475sh	470m	—
$[\text{Rh}(\text{BOX})(\text{CO})_2]^c$	615s 598m	520sh 510m	—	420w	—
$[\text{Rh}(\text{acac})(\text{CO})_2]^c$	620s	500s	495sh 485w	458m	—
$[\text{RhCl}(\text{CO})(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})_2]$	554s (2 020) ^e	508m	480m	—	425s ^d
$[\text{RhCl}(\text{CO})(i\text{-Pr}_2\text{SO})_2]$	560s (2 020) ^e	520s	504s	445m	410m ^d 320m

(Contd.)

		Table—1 (Contd.)			
[RhBr(CO)(<i>n</i> -Pr ₂ SO) ₂]	548s (2 023) ^e	502m	496s	—	420m ^d
[RhCl(CO)(<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SO) ₂]	560s (2 020) ^e	515m	490m	450m	410m ^d 380s 305m 410s ^d
[RhBr(CO)(<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SO) ₂]	550s (2 022) ^e	510s	480s	460m	303
[RhCl(CO)(PMe ₃) ₂] ^f	574vs (1 952) ^e	556m	498m	—	—
[RhBr(CO)(PMe ₃) ₂] ^f	566vs (1 961) ^e	550w	486m	—	—
[RhCl(CO)(Me ₂ S) ₂]	572s (1 972) ^e	542s	490m	—	425s ^d
[RhBr(CO)(Me ₂ S) ₂]	560s (1 974) ^e	535w	470w	—	425s ^d
[RhCl(CO)(<i>i</i> -Pr ₂ S) ₂]	575s (1 950) ^e	536m	500w	425vw	425s ^d
[RhBr(CO)(<i>i</i> -Pr ₂ S) ₂]	570s (1 951) ^e	530m	—	—	290s 426s ^d

^a ν_{δ} of BF₄⁻. ^bRef. 7. ^cRef. 10. ^d $\nu_{\text{Rh-S}}$. ^e ν_{CO} . ^fPersonal communication from Dr. J. Browning, The University of Bristol.

carbonyl complexes, [Rh(N-N)(CO)₂]⁺ and [Rh(LL)(CO)₂], where N-N=Me₂phen, NO₂-phen etc., LL=singly charged bidentate anionic ligands⁸, the location of Rh-C-O deformation can be ascertained fairly accurately. In case of hexacarbonyl of chromium and molybdenum and pentacarbonyl of iron, the M-C-O deformations⁹⁻¹¹ bands lie above 480 cm⁻¹ and $\nu_{\text{M-C}}$ stretching frequencies occur below 480 cm⁻¹ and upto 340 cm⁻¹.

We have assigned the bands to Rh-C-O deformation modes (Table 1) on the basis of following considerations : (i) if for dicarbonyls, the Rh(CO)₂ fragment is assumed to possess local C_{2v} symmetry, this should give rise to a maximum of four vibrations with at least one having weak intensity⁴ and (ii) in case of monocarbonyl derivatives, the linear Rh-C-O fragment should show two deformation vibrations^{2,3} (out-of-plane occurring at higher frequency range and in-plane occurring at a lower frequency range) and two Rh-C stretching (symmetric and antisymmetric) bands. It may be pointed out that the assignments of M-C-O deformation modes in [RhX(CO)(PR₃)₂] becomes difficult because of the presence of bands due to vibrations of phosphine groups. However, in case of complexes containing R₂S and R₂SO these assignments become straight forward. Table 1 shows that the $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ bands occur for dicarbonyl and monocarbonyl complexes in the ranges 575-622 and 548-575 cm⁻¹ respectively. The value of $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ bands is dependent on the amount of $d_{\pi-p_{\pi}}$ bonding between metal and carbonyl group and also upon electron donation of the type $\pi_{\nu}(\text{CO}) \rightarrow \text{Vacant } p_z(\text{Rh})$ ^{4,12}. It is interesting to note that in monocarbonyl complexes, the $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ bands are found to shift to lower energy^{4,13} in the bromo derivative compared to chloro complexes, but a reverse trend is observed for ν_{CO} bands in the corresponding complexes¹⁴. This can be explained by the fact that Br⁻ is stronger π -acceptor than Cl⁻ and competes more strongly with CO group for d_{π} -electrons of rhodium(I) which in turn decreases

the degree of interaction of Rh(d_{π} filled) \rightarrow CO (vacant π^*). This interaction weakens the bonding Rh-C and results in lower $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ and higher bond order of CO and consequently higher ν_{CO} bands. It is evident from the Table 1 that in square-planar complexes, [RhX(CO)L₂], X=Cl⁻, Br⁻; L=R₂S, R₂SO, the magnitude of shift of ν_{CO} from chloro to bromo derivative is much lower compared to the corresponding shifts of $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ bands. This shows that the change of halide ion in the complexes has greater impact on $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ band

Fig. 1. A general relationship between $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ and ν_{CO} bands.

compared to ν_{CO} bands. On the other hand, in passing from the complexes containing R_2SO to those R_2S , a greater shift (about $50\text{--}70\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of ν_{CO} bands compared to the corresponding shift (about $15\text{--}25\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ bands is observed. Thus, it reflects clearly the effect of change of ligands on $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ and ν_{CO} bands. A simple relationship between $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ and ν_{CO} for the monocarbonyl complexes is shown in Fig. 1.

Experimental

All the compounds were prepared according to the reported methods^{1,4}. Hydrated rhodium trichloride (Johnson Mathey), analytically pure Me_2Phen , $\text{NO}_2\text{-Phen}$, biq (E. Merck), all sulphoxides and sulphides (Aldrich) were used without further purification. The solvents were purified by standard methods. Elemental analysis were done at C.S.I.R.O., Australia.

Ir spectra (nujol/CsI) were recorded on Specord 75 IR and Beckman IR 20 spectrophotometers.

References

1. L. M. VALLARINO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 161.
2. D. M. ADAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1771.
3. A. M. MANNING, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1670.
4. Y. S. VARSHAVSKII, M. M. SINGH and N. A. BUZINA, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1971, **16**, 1372.
5. M. J. CLEARE and W. P. GRIFFITH, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 372.
6. M. A. BANNET and R. J. H. CLARK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 5560.
7. J. BROWNING, P. L. GOGGIN, R. J. GOODFELLOW, M. G. NORTON, A. J. M. RATTRAY, B. F. TAYLOR and J. MINK, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, **20**, 2061.
8. K. GOSWAMI, Ph.D. Thesis, Dibrugarh University, 1978; K. GOSWAMI and M. M. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1718.
9. D. M. ADAMS and L. H. JONES, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **36**, 2375.
10. H. MURATA and K. KAWAI, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, **27**, 605.
11. W. F. EDGELL, W. E. WILSON and R. SUMMIT, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1963, **19**, 863.
12. A. A. GRINBERG, M. M. SINGH and YU. S. VARSHAVSKY, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1968, **13**, 2716.
13. K. GOSWAMI and M. M. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 477.
14. D. K. DUTTA and M. M. SINGH, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1979, **4**, 330; 1980, **5**, 244.

Preparation and Infrared Spectra of the Schiff Base Solid Complexes $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ and $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{Et}_3\text{N})]$ ($\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn} = n, n'\text{-}o\text{-Phenylenebissalicylideneiminato}$)

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The preparation and chemistry of Schiff base complexes of the main transition elements have been extensively investigated¹. Most of these studies are focused on the complexes of the *d*-block elements and little attention has been given to the spectral studies of Schiff base complexes of the *f*-block elements. Uranium(VI) in many Schiff base complexes could be six² or seven coordinates^{3,4}. In both cases the tetradentate Schiff base occupies the four equatorial positions, while the two oxygens (of UO_2 unit) take the two axial positions. However, in the case of U^{VI} being seven-coordinate, a monodentate ligand (could be the solvent) occupies an additional equatorial position⁵.

Bandoli *et al.*⁶ reported the formation and crystal structure of the complex $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{EtOH})]$. In the present communication, we report the preparation of the related two new complexes $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}$

$o\text{-phdn})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ and $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{Et}_3\text{N})]$, where $\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn} = N, N'\text{-}o\text{-phenylenebis(salicylideneiminato)}$; here U^{VI} is seven-coordinate. The infrared spectra of these two complexes are recorded and assigned.

Results and Discussion

The infrared spectral data of the complexes $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ and $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{Et}_3\text{N})]$ are given in Table 1. Bandoli *et al.*⁶ reported the crystal structure of the related complex $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{EtOH})]$ which indicates that the four donor atoms of the Schiff base (two nitrogens and two oxygens) and the oxygen of the EtOH are coordinated to U^{VI} in a plane forming an irregular pentagon with the uranyl group perpendicular to this plane. The infrared spectrum of $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$

TABLE 1—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF COMPLEXES [UO₂(sal-*o*-phdn)(L)](L=H₂O AND Et₃N)

L=H ₂ O	L=Et ₃ N	Assignment
3 642w		$\nu_{as}(\text{OH})$; coord. H ₂ O
3 561w br		$\nu_s(\text{OH})$; coord. H ₂ O
	3 450m br	
3 095w	3 073vw	$\nu(\text{CH})$; phenyl
	3 063w	
3 046w	3 034w	
3 017w	3 009vw	
2 994w	2 997vw	$\nu(\text{CH})$; =CH-
	2 916m	$\nu(\text{C-H})$; (CH ₂), (CH ₃); Et ₃ N
	2 848m	
	2 805w	
1 605s	1 605s	$\nu(\text{C=N})$; azomethine
1 572s	1 574ms	phenyl breathing modes
	1 555ms	
1 540s	1 536s	
1 500w		
1 470s	1 464s	
	1 440ms	
1 420s		
1 382m	1 377s	CH deformations; CH, CH ₂
1 360m	1 368w	
1 340w	1 334w	
	1 306s	
1 280s	1 281w	$\nu(\text{C-C})$, $\nu(\text{C-O})$ and $\nu(\text{C-N})$
1 262m	1 254w	
1 225w	1 228w	
1 216m		
1 175m	1 188s	
1 155m		
1 149ms	1 146s	
1 123w	1 112w	
1 106m		
1 094w	1 096w	
1 063w		CH bend; phenyl
1 048w		
1 034w	1 025w	
1 013m		
989w	972m	$\nu_{as}(\text{U=O})$
960m	941w	
912s	918ms	$\nu_s(\text{U=O})$
896vs	893s	
827m	830m	
810m	805ms	CH bend, phenyl
788m		
768m	756s	
730s		
669w	669m	CH in-plane bends; phenyl
637w	650w	
627w		
617m	601w	
596w	579w	
568w	557w	
516w	530m	$\nu_{as}(\text{U-O})$; O of Schiff base
504m	481w	
468m	474w	$\nu_s(\text{U-O})$; O of Schiff base
	437m	CH out-of-plane bends; phenyl
417m	411w	
	388m	
	388m	
374w	375w	
363w	353m	
336m	337w	
	327w	
300m	305m	$\nu_{as}(\text{U-N})$; N of Schiff base
	282m	$\nu(\text{U-N})$; N of Et ₃ N
276m	273w	$\nu_s(\text{U-N})$; N of Schiff base

m≡medium. s≡strong. w≡weak. v≡very. br≡broad.

complex shows differences compared with that previously published for the EtOH complex⁷. The two characteristic bands of coordinated water are observed at 3 642 and 3 561 cm⁻¹ besides the known bands for the Schiff base (Table 1). However, H₂O is expected to coordinate to U^{VI} equatorially in a way similar to EtOH complex (I). Thus the H₂O complex contains two plane of symmetry and one C₂ axis of symmetry, hence the complex may belong to C_{2v} symmetry.

I

The ir spectrum of the complex [UO₂-(sal-*o*-phdn)(Et₃N)] shows many differences compared with that of the H₂O complex. The spectrum does not show the bands of coordinated water and instead, for example, a group of bands related to ν_{CH} of C₂H₅ groups of Et₃N are observed at 2 916, 2 848 and 2 805 cm⁻¹ (Table 1). In this complex Et₃N is expected to coordinate to U^{VI} equatorially⁶. Accordingly, this complex contains only a plane of symmetry and thus the complex belongs to the C_s symmetry. The four vibrations of the UO₂ unit in the complex [(UO₂(sal-*o*-phdn)(H₂O)] which belongs to the C_{2v} symmetry are of the type ²A₁, B₁ and B₂ modes. These are $\nu_s(\text{U=O})$; A₁, $\nu_{as}(\text{U=O})$; B₁, $\delta(\text{UO}_2)$; A₁ and $\delta(\text{UO}_2)$; B₂. The $\nu_s(\text{U=O})$ occurs at 827 cm⁻¹ while the corresponding $\nu_{as}(\text{U=O})$ is assigned to the strong doublet at 912 and 896 cm⁻¹. The doublet structure of $\nu_{\text{U=O}}$ may infer the existence of solid-solid interaction⁴ involving the uranyl oxygens of one complex and U^{VI} of another. In the complex [(UO₂(sal-*o*-phdn)(Et₃N)] which belongs to the C_s symmetry, the four vibrations of the uranyl unit, UO₂, are of the type ³A' and A''. These are $\nu_s(\text{U=O})$; A' $\nu_{as}(\text{U=O})$; A', $\delta(\text{UO}_2)$; A' and $\delta(\text{UO}_2)$; A''. The $\nu_{as}(\text{U=O})$ occurs at 918 and 893 cm⁻¹ while the $\nu_s(\text{U=O})$ is observed as medium band at 830 cm⁻¹. These assignments for the different U=O vibrations agree with the known values for related complexes^{7,8}. The frequency values of the $\nu_{\text{U=O}}$ were used to calculate the length and force constant, F_{U-O}, for the uranyl bonds in the two complexes according to the known method⁹. The calculated values are 661.7 Nm⁻¹ and 1.745 Å for the aqua-complex and 666.5 Nm⁻¹ and 1.744 Å for the Et₃N complex. These values are close to those known⁴ for the related uranyl complexes.

The ν_{CH} vibrations for the phenyl groups in the two complexes are assigned in the range 3 095–3 009

cm^{-1} (Table 1), while those of the (=CH-) unit are found at 2994 cm^{-1} for the aqua-complex and at 2997 cm^{-1} for the Et_3N complex. The ν_{CH} of CH_3- and $-\text{CH}_2-$ for the Et_3N complex are found at $2916-2805\text{ cm}^{-1}$, while these bands are absent in the H_2O complex. The $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C}=\text{N})$ of the azomethine for the Et_3N complex are found at 1605 cm^{-1} as strong band. This motion belongs to A' symmetry (C_s symmetry), while for the H_2O complex, the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C}=\text{N})$ is observed at 1605 cm^{-1} and belongs to B_2 symmetry (under the C_{2v} symmetry). For the assignments of the breathing vibrations of the phenyl groups, a group of bands appear at $1574-1464\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The CH-deformations of the =CH- and CH_3 groups appear at $1382-1306\text{ cm}^{-1}$, while the CH-bends in-plane bands are found at $669-557\text{ cm}^{-1}$, but those for the out-of-plane motions occur at $437-327\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The various vibrations due to $\nu_{\text{C-C}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ for the Schiff base in the two complexes appear at $1281-1094\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The antisymmetric stretching vibration, $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{U-O})$, (oxygen of Schiff base) occurs around 516 and 530 cm^{-1} for H_2O and Et_3N complexes respectively, while that corresponding to symmetric motion, $\nu_s(\text{U-O})$ is observed at 468 cm^{-1} for H_2O complex and at 474 cm^{-1} for Et_3N complex. $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{U-N})$ and $\nu_s(\text{U-N})$ (N of Schiff base) bands occur around 305 and 273 cm^{-1} for the two complexes, while the corresponding $\nu(\text{U-N})$ (N of Et_3N) is observed at 282 cm^{-1} . From the above data the stretching vibration, $\nu(\text{U-O})$, are assigned at higher values compared with that of $\nu(\text{U-N})$. These assignments agree with those known for the related complexes^{4,5}, where the U-O (oxygen of Schiff base) bond is expected to be stronger than the U-N (N of Schiff base).

Experimental

All chemicals were of A.R. grade. The Schiff base $\text{sal-}o\text{-phdnH}_2$ (N,N' - o -phenylenebis(salicylideneimine)) was prepared by the condensation of o -phenylenediamine with salicylaldehyde, according to the known method¹⁰. The uranyl complex $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ was obtained by stirring mixture of $\text{UO}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.06 g, 4 mmol) in acetone

and stoichiometric amount of the Schiff base (0.79 g, 4 mmol) in acetone at room temperature. The resulting orange-red crystals were washed with acetone and dried under reduced pressure. The other complex $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{Et}_3\text{N})]$ (orange colour) was prepared in a similar way by the reaction of $\text{UO}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with the Schiff base and Et_3N in 1:1:1 molar ratio using acetone as a solvent. The two complexes were characterised by their ir spectra and elemental analysis: Found (calcd.) $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$, C, 39.12 (39.86); H, 2.47 (2.65); N, 4.25 (4.65); $[\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-}o\text{-phdn})(\text{Et}_3\text{N})]$, C, 45.10 (45.54); H, 4.38 (4.23); N, 5.96 (6.13).

The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer.

References

1. S. M. CRAWFORD, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1963, **19**, 255; A. BIGOTTO, V. GALASSO and G. DEALTY, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1972, **28**, 1581; S. V. SHEAT and T. N. WATERS, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1221; S. M. ABU-EL-WAFA, R. M. ISSA and C. A. MCAULIFFE, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **99**, 103; R. E. HESTER and E. M. NOUR, *J. Raman Spectrosc.*, 1981, **11**, 49.
2. E. M. NOUR, I. S. ALNAIMI and N. A. ALEM, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, 1991, communicated.
3. G. BANDOLI, D. A. CLEMENTE, U. GROATTO, M. VIDALI and P. A. VIGATO, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 2331.
4. E. M. NOUR, A. A. TAHA and I. S. ALNAIMI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **141**, 139.
5. H. ALMADFA, A. A. SAID and E. M. NOUR, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1991, **128**, 137.
6. G. BANDOLI, D. A. CLEMENTE, U. GROATTO, M. VIDALI and P. A. VIGATO, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1971, 1330.
7. R. J. HILL and C. E. F. RICKARD, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 793.
8. E. M. NOUR and A. N. ABDEL-RAHMAN, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1984, **116**, 377.
9. S. P. MCGLYNN, J. K. SMITH and W. C. NEELY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 105; L. H. JONES, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1959, **15**, 409.
10. P. FREIFFER, E. BREITH, E. LUBBE and T. TSUMOKI, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1933, **503**, 84.